

Unlocking Knowledge: Professional Perspectives on Pakistan's Open Access Institutional Repositories

Hidayatullah

M. Phil Scholar, Department of Library Information Science,
University of Balochistan Quetta.

Abdul Baqi

Assistant Professor, Faculty of Library & Information Science,
University of Balochistan Quetta

Abstract

Open Access Institutional Repositories (OA-IRs) play a crucial role in disseminating scholarly research, yet their adoption in Pakistan remains limited. This study explores the status and awareness of OA-IRs in Pakistan through a professional perspective in public and private sector. Organizations showcase their intellectual works using the Open access institutional repository platform. Using quantitative based method the present study focuses on the current status and awareness of open access institutional repositories of Pakistan. Data was interpreted by using "content Analysis" technique and results has provided. Structured questionnaire has generated for the collection of data through Google form. Library professionals provided the response about status and awareness about IR. Results of the current study are based on the status and awareness of the IR in Pakistan. The study revealed the IR developments in Pakistan. The population of present study was seven institutions of Pakistan in different provinces of the country so a questionnaire sent to each professional by email. This study was mostly quantitative therefor, SPSS software have used in analyzing and interpreting the data for drawing the interference accordingly. Through this study it became clear that there is lack of OAIR in Pakistan. However, some of institutions have established OAIR in Pakistan. Absences of OAIR in universities have extensively affecting the status and awareness of OAIR. Additionally, institutional repositories serve an essential role in advancing knowledge and research in the country, as they provide a platform for sharing information and fostering collaboration between institutions and researchers. OAIR can play a valuable role in changing Pakistan into an advanced country.

Keywords: Open Access Institutional Repositories, Scholarly Communication, Information Dissemination, Library Professionals in Pakistan, Repository Awareness and Adoption

Corresponding Author Email:

baqibaloch.shal@gmail.com

Journal of Quranic
and Social Studies
177-188

© The Author (s) 2024
Volume:4, Issue:2, 2024

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.

www.jqss.org

ISSN: E/ 2790-5640

ISSN: P/ 2790-5632

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